

USE OF CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In maintaining the economic growth of a country, education plays an important role. But in real life the practical knowledge, profound thinking, and some experience is required to remain in competition. In schools and even in the colleges, the traditional education system is applied which is proved useless many years ago. Nowadays the classroom teaching is changing and students are becoming more technology oriented and therefore in his changing environment, it's important that we think about the latest technologies to incorporate in the teaching and learning process. Because of the technology, it is possible to give the demonstration of the experiments, using presentation and the animation; it is now very easy to imagine the things. One of the latest technologies prevailing now days is Cloud Computing. By sharing IT services in the cloud, educational institution can outsource noncore services and better concentrate on offering students, teachers, faculty, and staff the essential tools to help them succeed. By using cloud computing. we can build the good education system and increase the quality of the system.

Covid-19 caused a big shift to the cloud. However, I must admit that even without the pandemic, cloud-based tools were surging in popularity. Cloud computing-based technologies are one of the demanded and actively developing areas of the modern IT world. The use of cloud technologies in the educational process is becoming more and more popular and opens up many opportunities, both for educational institutions, teachers, and students. Educational-oriented cloud technologies are predicted to hit \$25 billion by 2021.

So what does it mean for modern and future education-development and what are the main benefits of cloud technologies in education?

Examples of the Application of Cloud Technologies in Education. In this section, we'll take a look at some of the most popular cloud-based programs used in education.

Google Classroom. Google Classroom is a cloud-based learning management system that is a part of Google Apps for Education. Google Classroom enables students to access the platform from computers, tablets, and smartphones.

Blackboard. Blackboard provides education, mobile, communication, and commerce software and related services to clients, including education providers, corporations, and government organizations. In January 2014, its software and services are used by approximately 17,000 schools and organizations in 100 countries

Knowledge Matters. Knowledge Matters is a leading cloud-based virtual business online interactive, game-like business simulations teach college and high school students key business lessons.

Coursera. In my opinion, the most widely known education platform. On Coursera, you get access to a wide range of disciplines. There is hardly any student in the USA, Canada, Thailand, Russia, and Ukraine who is not aware of an opportunity to get precious knowledge with Coursera.

Microsoft Education Center. Microsoft Education Center is created to let students continue obtaining knowledge no matter what. They facilitate online learning and deliver the best education straight to every student.

Classflow. Classflow is a cloud-based interactive display lesson delivery software. They provide the users with access to lessons and learning resources 24/7 with no obligatory subscription.

Cloud computing growth in education. How the education sector responded to the challenges of 2020. It may have felt like time slowed down in 2020. But, across industries and sectors, the year caused many organizations to put the pedal to the floor when it comes to digital transformation. Education is no exception.

But with so many legacy systems and processes in place, innovation in education can feel as far off as summer break on the first day of school. Fortunately, many of the challenges COVID-19 has presented in education can be addressed with cloud.

Whether it's in K-12 and primary schools, higher education, or ed tech, cloud computing can transform education — for educators, students, and those who support them. It's probably no surprise then to hear that education-focused cloud computing is [projected](#) to hit an estimated market value of \$25 billion this year.

So what is the value of cloud and cloud solutions for the education industry today? And what does it take for organizations in education to adapt these approaches and reap the real benefits of cloud computing?

To break it down to the most elementary level, **the benefits of cloud in education are around achieving the maximum result with minimal expense.** The “results” can vary depending on your desired outcome but can include cost savings, security, flexibility, IT simplification, and more.

Here are some of the big benefits of cloud across higher education, K-12 and primary schools, and ed tech.

1. Gain flexibility. Cloud solutions for the education industry give organizations in the industry the flexibility to respond immediately to changes — like (just as a totally random example) moving suddenly from in-person to remote learning.

- **With the cloud, organizations can crank up or down resources as needed** without all the time-consuming, costly, and (sometimes) painfully bureaucratic planning required to set up on-premises hardware.

- Need access to bleeding-edge hardware to do the heavy lifting for research? **Cloud gives you access to the tech tools you need with a few mouse clicks, and you pay only for what you use.**

- The cloud also gives the elasticity to automatically increase your tech capabilities to handle a rush of demand. With on-premises hardware, a sudden, unexpected rush of people accessing a server can bring everything to a halt. But **the cloud can scale up to handle demand automatically** — or make adjustments based on your criteria.

2. Reduce costs and complexity. Cloud gives organizations flexibility — the kind ideal in budget-conscious organizations with ever-shifting needs, shrinking budgets, and ballooning demands. (Sound familiar?) When you only have to pay for what you use, you can have access to tools when you need them and not pay for them when you don't. Think about it like ordering a Lyft rather than buying a car.

- **A traditional IT approach to scaling up is expensive and slow.** It takes planning, requires hardware at an upfront cost, and IT specialists to set it up and keep it running. With cloud, much of that work is handled by your cloud provider (e.g., Amazon Web Services or Microsoft Azure).

- [Humber College](#) in Canada was able to save \$500,000 annually and improve their IT helpdesk service by investing in cloud.

- It's important to note here, without the technical staff needed to plan and execute your cloud migration properly, [cloud spend can get out of control](#). This is where building up cloud skills is essential. Moving to the cloud isn't inherently a money-saving move if done sloppily. (To oversimplify things a bit, let's return to our above example: taking a Lyft can be more expensive than owning a car if you're taking multiple too many long trips a day.) However, **cloud allows organizations to move from CapEx to a OpEx model** — or to move from big upfront investments to smaller, predictable monthly ones.

- Maintaining tech is (literally) a full-time job. **Cloud simplifies IT and frees up educational IT staff to focus on organizational objectives** — rather than the tedious maintenance of hardware and software.

3. Ensure reliability, security, and compliance. The major public cloud providers run worldwide, world-class networks of cutting-edge facilities. They serve thousands of organizations in the education industry, which means they're most likely able to meet any reliability, security, or compliance requirements you might have.

- Keeping sensitive student or financial data in the cloud rather than on a hard drive can **prevent data from getting compromised if a device is stolen or misplaced.**

- Cloud providers are able to **keep latency low and deliver near unparalleled data backup and disaster recovery.**

- As opposed to custom-built solutions that may be frankenstein-ed together, cloud providers can ensure your **tools are easily accessible to students, parents, teachers, and faculty anywhere on nearly any device** (with an internet connection, obviously).

How is **cloud computing used in higher education**? Innovative approaches allow organizations to turn challenges into opportunities for improvement. How's that work in higher education?

[John Kitchen](#) — director of client success, ITS, at Widener University — sums it up well: “Higher education is facing a truly unprecedented situation this school year. **Now is the time for academic IT leaders to consider the financial and operational benefits of cloud migration that can help institutions stay online and thrive.**”

How can higher education benefit from the cloud?

- **Implement new platforms and tools.** Cloud offers higher-ed institutions the ability to develop deeper connections via new digital platforms tools and simplifies technology for educators, students, and higher-ed IT staff.
- **Boost productivity and resilience.** At the [University of Toronto](#), investing in Microsoft cloud solutions has helped increase the ability to be resilient amongst unforeseen challenges. “Over the last few years, the University has made significant enhancements to our infrastructure that will help us get through challenging times, not the least of which is moving to cloud services that are scalable during events like this pandemic,” said Bo Wandschneider, CIO at the University of Toronto
- **Reduce costs with a pay-as-you-go model.** The simplification that comes with cloud brings with it some financial benefits. Moving to the cloud can help higher-ed institutions spend their tech investments more wisely, making up for the reduction in funds typically brought in through everything from parking to dining. It also empowers institutions to more easily spin up online-only classes to attract students who might not be ready or able to go back on campus.
- **Advance research with high-performance computing**
Cloud providers can offer the high-performance computers needed to process complex scientific workloads. And with the ability to store (and share) petabytes of data, cloud makes it easier to share results and collaborate with others around the globe.
- **Tap into machine learning and artificial intelligence**
Pulling in more data allows higher-ed institutions to use the power of artificial intelligence (A.I.) and machine learning in education. This can allow for things like learning and content analytics for personalized learning, active learning and experimental design to make learning more efficient, or data mining for cognitive psychology research.
- **Get answers from Big Data and predictive analytics**
Tapping into machine learning in education allows you to get answers out of your data. Cloud tools can help academic IT create and run solutions that can benefit higher-ed organizations — including educational data mining for student success prediction models and analytics that deliver insights around things like student retention and engagement.
- **Launch fully remote instruction.** For higher ed, fully remote instruction can include entirely virtual courses that are (potentially) offered at a more affordable rate to students with less drain on school resources for the institution. These courses can be offered as on-demand lectures that work with nontraditional student schedules. For an example, see The University of Texas at Austin’s [Master of Science in Computer Science Online](#) program. The university is able to cut fees and overhead while providing flexibility to attract students —

and potentially bring in students who may be not eager to get back to an in-person learning environment just yet. It also gives students the option to earn a relatively affordable advanced degree at \$10,000 USD.

- **Spin up virtual computer labs.** Support online distance learning by creating virtual campus computer labs. These consist of centrally managed desktops and applications that are secure and accessible via any computer's web browser. This allows organizations to scale up as needed without buying and setting up hardware or IT infrastructure.
- **Create cloud-based contact centers.** Quickly set up cloud-based contact centers for everything from IT helpdesk to financial aid and provide students, parents, faculty, and staff inbound and outbound support.
- **Get more affordable access to the latest tools.** For students and faculty in higher ed, switching from quickly outdated physical books and software to cloud-based tools carries multiple benefits, including accessing tools across multiple devices and offering more affordable access options. With cloud-based versions of industry-specific applications, students can get hands-on with up-to-date professional tools without paying an arm and a leg for a one-time license. Tools like Adobe Creative Cloud are available as a subscription model, freeing students to pay for a few months during a course — or, as in the case of [Autodesk](#), some tools are potentially accessible for free.
- **Increase the efficiency of IT management.** Migrating to the cloud can help alleviate higher-ed IT resources for heavy processes — like having the structure in place to handle huge spikes in traffic during class registration. To ensure you're getting the maximum benefits and ROI of [cloud migration](#), ensure IT staff has the know-how needed to marry legacy IT systems and cloud solutions.
- **Drive innovation with a DevOps approach.** While higher ed can traditionally be change-averse, an organizational shift toward a DevOps philosophy can be hugely beneficial to increase the speed of innovation. [DevOps](#) brings software development and IT operations together to reduce the time needed to go from idea to implementation with things like [CI/CD](#), [site reliability engineering](#), and [automation](#) achieved through tools like [PowerShell](#) and [Puppet](#).

How is **cloud computing used in K-12 and primary schools**? Cloud brings with it a wide range of benefits to K-12 and primary schools and districts, benefits that are even more noticeable in the new normal of remote and hybrid learning environments.

- **80% of school ed tech leaders report using cloud to increase efficiencies**, and the cloud market in the education sector has grown at a [projected](#) CAGR rate of more than 26% from 2017 to this year.

Teachers know how to teach. School and district IT teams just need to invest in giving them the tools that allow them to take those skills and make them work in a remote or hybrid environment.

Benefits of Cloud Technologies in Modern Education. Let's start with the benefits that teachers face with the implementation of cloud technologies in the modern education system. First of all, teachers gain higher chances to attract the attention of a student making

the education process fun. School teachers as well as university professors are able to prepare online tests, create better content, and communicate with students online.

Cloud technologies help also cover a wider audience of students and manage their process of studying. Assess the tests, homework, projects taken by students, sending the feedback has never been that easy.

Administrators, in their turn, can easily collaborate with one another and save money and time on the problem-solving process. Cloud technologies make it fast and in re.

Access to Information. According to Network providers, the Internet is available 99.9% of the time which is very convenient for all participants of the educational process. This aspect should be investigated deeper by explaining several aspects.

First, both students and teachers can realize learning opportunities practically at any time, not depending on local information and educational resources institutions. As a result, this leads to tremendous time savings. Besides, constant availability removes barriers to access to information for students who are physically unable to attend classes in person. Since the cloud-based application for e-learning runs with cloud power, the software is automatically updated in the cloud source. [E-learners](#) get updates fast.

Second, sharing notes has never been easier. Handwriting notes are taken from a mate first needed to be copied manually or photocopied. Cloud technologies have changed it forever. Now you can share or receive notes from every area covered with the Internet connection.

Third, data safety is no longer a problem since they're all gathered and stored on the cloud, you don't need to bother with keeping everything on your PC.

Online Education Courses. .Online Education Courses have been booming during recent years. It's not only about Coursera (that we'll discuss later) but also about education courses not connected to school, college, or university education. With cloud technologies, every one of us has an access to online SMM, SEO, IT (and [HTML cheat sheets](#)) courses, Instagram online courses (the majority of which are like purchasing the air, no offense), and other courses that improve your employability.

Speaking of Coursera, this is, by far, the largest project in the sphere of online education developed in 2012. By 2017, the service could boast of 24 million attracted visitors. The project includes courses in physics, engineering disciplines, humanities and arts, medicine, biology, mathematics, computer science, economics, and business. Coursera runs on the Nginx web server on Linux machines rented from Amazon Web Services. The data is stored in Amazon S3 and the site is searched using Amazon CloudSearch.

Competitiveness. Education is not the only sphere that successfully integrates cloud technologies. Businesses are now widely adopting the cloud computing model spending less money, acquiring flexibility, and advanced security. This has given a powerful impulse for cloud computing to develop.

Nowadays, education using cloud technologies can compete with the traditional educational process. We also shouldn't forget that cloud technologies make high-quality self-education possible. Employers are no more suspicious about potential workers who prefer e-learning instead of attending classes and eagerly offer them prestigious job positions.

Reduced Time and Costs. Since the main concept of cloud technologies means connecting to cloud-based applications, neither students nor teachers have a need for specific devices to access the material. Cloud-based programs are perfectly compatible with any device. Even the cheap smartphone allows you to connect to related academic applications.

No Need For Expensive Software. The SaaS model is considered to be one of the biggest advantages of cloud-based computing. It's common for software applications to be available for students for low-fee or free basis making the education affordable for most students.

Saving Money on Expensive Textbooks. It's a commonly known fact that university-level textbooks are an expensive pleasure. They have outpaced almost any other element of the university involved in university education including tuition fees. This results in more and more students refraining from buying them. Cloud-based textbooks are the only solution to this problem. Digital books are usually less expensive. Hence, lower-income students are also able to [gain access to high learning quality](#). Implementation of cloud technologies eliminates financial inequality putting students of all status into the same educational environment.

Conclusion. The worldwide lockdown due to the coronavirus pandemic made us oversee the concept of e-learning. Cloud computing is widely used in businesses, is also a must-have in the education process. Cloud technologies make education a simple and fun experience for participants from both sides of the learning process. Students, professors, and teachers are now able to appreciate the accessibility and ease of cloud-based education.

Yet cloud applications and the opportunities that they provide in the educational process are endless, summing up, I would like to identify the most relevant advantages of the "cloud". These are improved accessibility, administration, high competitiveness, time, and money-saving. The instant feedback, precious information, and low-cost textbooks make high-class education available for everyone.

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